

EPIDEMIOLOGY AND TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL PROBLEMS OF THE FORMATION OF ILEOTRANSVERZOANASTOMOSES IN INTESTINAL SURGERY (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The authors report that today there is a steady increase in intestinal diseases requiring surgical treatment. At the same time, there is a steady increase in the number of stomatological patients who require reconstructive surgery. It is alarming that disagreements remain in determining the timing of the RVR, there are no specific recommendations on a therapeutic and diagnostic algorithm of actions and a perfect ITA method modeling the valve function of the bauginia flap. The authors conclude that the search continues, and it is justified, because it is aimed at improving the results of surgical treatment of this contingent of patients.*

Keywords: *right-sided hemicolectomy, ileotransverzoanastomosis, anastomosis failure, invagination anastomosis.*

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the number of patients with intestinal stoma is increasing worldwide [Fedorov E.V., 2019]. To date, there has been a steady increase in intestinal diseases requiring surgical treatment [Solovyov I.A., 2018; Torchinsky N.V., 2020]. Among tumors of the colon, up to 31% are lesions of its right half, and the most fatal (from 5 to 20%) is tumor decay [Vorobyov G.I., 2008; Selnyagina L.A., 2015]. At the same time, cancer patients undergoing right-sided hemicolectomy account for 92% [Cherdantsev D.V., 2017; Kaprin V.V., 2019]. Also, the active surgical zone is the ileum [Aliyev F.Sh., 2017; Spirev V.V., 2017].

In 1931, in the monograph *Chirurgie du rectum*, H. Hartmann expressed the opinion that after the operation he proposed, it is possible to restore the natural passage [Polovinkin V.V., 2016]. Unfortunately, there is a steady increase in the number of stomatological patients requiring reconstructive surgery (RVR), and more than 50% of them are people of working age [Gibert B.K., 2017; Garmanova T.N., 2019].

In the literature it is noted that in some diseases and injuries, it is the formation of an ileostomy that is a necessary stage of treatment [Aliyev F.Sh., 2016]. In particular, the causes of intestinal stoma are benign tumors of the colon and its complications – in 12-27%, acute intestinal obstruction (OCD) of non-tumor etiology - in 6-18%, complicated course of inflammatory bowel diseases – in almost 10% [Timerbulatov M.V., 2018] and intestinal injuries with violation of its integrity - 55.2% among all cases [Timerbulatov M.V., 2018].

Ileostomy, as an option for completing surgery for OCD and peritonitis, is primarily used for localization of pathology in the distal parts of the small and colon. When ileostomy is formed, complications are possible that worsen the outcome of treatment. At the same time, the results of treatment are influenced by such factors as the patient's gender and age, body weight and condition of the abdominal cavity [Totikov V.Z. et al., 2013].

Ileostomy as an option for completing surgery for acute intestinal obstruction and peritonitis is primarily used for localization of pathology in the distal parts of the small intestine.

According to Vorobyov G.I. (2008), there are more than 200 methods of intestinal stomas, each of them has its advantages and disadvantages. The main task of the COP is to prevent the insolvency of the interstitial joint [Vorobyov G.I., 2008].

Surgeons specializing in colon surgery note that these operations are among the most difficult. The reason for this is the lack of a common view on the choice of recovery time, in the choice of surgical access, and the method of formation of an inter-intestinal anastomosis. Disagreement in the definition of surgical tactics explains the relatively high incidence of suture failure in 6-25% of cases, purulent-inflammatory complications in 26-40% and mortality in 3-7%, averaging 5.2% [Fedorov E.V., 2019; Tomnyuk N.A., 2021].

Ileotransversoanastomoses are classified by: 1) the method of formation: manual and mechanical; 2) the type of formation: end to end, end to side, side to side; 3) the number of rows of stitches: one-, two- and three-row; 4) the nature of the seams: nodular, continuous, seamless; 5) the depth of capture into the seam of intestinal layers walls: gray-serous, serous-muscular, mucosal-submucosal, without capture of the mucous membrane, through all layers of the intestinal wall; 6) location of nodules: nodules outward, nodules inward (into the lumen of the intestine). According to the presence of valvular properties, thin-intestinal anastomoses should be divided into two groups: those that do not have valvular properties and those with valvular properties [Fedorov V.D., 1994].

Choosing the optimal tactics for restoring the continuity of the intestinal tract is an important task of surgical rehabilitation of patients with intestinal stomas. To solve it, various approaches are used to reduce the likelihood of complications. The development of complications depends on the method of IT formation [Ilchenko A.A., 2009].

Surgical tactics vary from the formation of a stoma to a radical operation with the formation of an ITA [Spirev V.V., 2017; Mao D., 2022]. It should be noted that with peritonitis, it becomes necessary to perform a resection volume of intervention, while with intestinal obstruction, it is possible to limit oneself to a proximal stoma at the first stage [Kondratyuk A.I., 2018].

When performing intestinal resection, there are 3 possible options for completing the operation: 1) the formation of an ITA (in particular, a U-shaped one, with an additional enterostomy); 2) stage-by-stage surgery, providing for obstructive resection of the intestine without stomation with intubation of the adductor loop, rehabilitation of the abdominal cavity and the formation of an anastomosis in the near future (up to 4 days); 3) resection with the formation of a stoma and its closure in the long term [Glushkov N.I., 2018].

The optimal way to end the operation is to form an anastomosis, however, the frequency of its failure in conditions of peritonitis reaches up to 15% [Agaev E.K., 2022]. In such situations, an ileostomy is often formed [Tsarkov P.V., 2017; Zhu Y., 2022].

Performing RVR in 10% of cases can also be complicated by the failure of the anastomosis and one in ten of them dies [Tang T., 2020; Rajan R., 2022].

Laparoscopic surgery, including the formation of ITA during laparoscopic right-sided hemicolectomy, is becoming the standard of treatment for many surgical diseases [Emile S., 2019]. Defects in the hardware laparoscopic mechanical suture during the formation of an anastomosis after hemicolectomy are detected in 18% of observations [Korolev P.A., 2018; Siegel R.L., 2019]. Due to the high cost of equipment, the manual method remains the main method of forming the interstitial joint everywhere [Baumann P., 2018].

The first compression device is known as the "Murphy's button", its modification by Kanshin H.H. became internationally known as the AKA device [Volenko P.A., 2006; Niezbekov B.M., 2020]. The development of endoscopic methods made it possible to recognize laparoscopic right-sided hemicolectomy as the standard of surgical treatment for cancer of the right colon [Yakomaskin V.N., 2019; Shin J.K., 2018].

Compared with open surgeries, the advantage of laparoscopic interventions is noted in reducing the frequency of postoperative complications, primarily due to a decrease in the frequency of infectious complications and postoperative intestinal obstruction [Davis C.H., 2018]. In any case, anamnesis and preoperative data can only allow us to determine indirect signs of the technical complexity of the upcoming operation. When starting reconstructive intervention, regardless of the chosen access, we always have a certain degree of uncertainty about the severity of the adhesive process and the condition of the immediate area of the operation. Solving these tasks "on the spot" represents the experience and skill of a surgeon [Stoiko Yu.M., 2019].

Intracorporeal anastomosis was the next step in the development of laparoscopic colon surgery [Salamakhin M.P., 2020; Wu Q., 2017]. The technique began to develop actively in the world, the number of publications on the request "intracorporeal anastomosis" in the largest Pubmed database from 2015 to 2020 is 363 articles [Gordeev S.A., 2020].

In 2013, a review was published [Tarta C, 2013], which analyzed data from 13 centers and 611 laparoscopic hemicolectomies performed about oncological and non-oncological diseases.

Qualification of surgeons

There was also a difference, the frequency of anastomosis failure ranged from 0 to 8.5%. The authors concluded that laparoscopic hemicolectomy requires a highly qualified operating surgeon. The frequency of failure of the interstitial anastomoses, when using hardware methods, is noted in 1.5- 15.2% of cases with a mortality rate of 0-4.7%, suppuration of the postoperative wound - in 2.5-25% and impaired patency of anastomoses - in 2.5-20% of cases [Manikhas G.M., 2010].

It is important to note that to this day, the problem of surgical rehabilitation of stomatized patients has not been completely solved and is relevant, due to the fact that these surgical interventions are no less complex than primary operations [Gibert B.K., 2018; Abdullazhanov B.R., 2020].

Another likely risk factor for postoperative complications is the timing of reconstructive operations, which can be performed in terms of up to 3 months, more than 3 months, after 6 months, as well as in terms of more than 1 year or more [Akhmetzhanov F.Sh., 2017; Moro-Valdezate D., 2019]. Scientific research continues to be conducted in this area in clinics and laboratories of our Republic, as well as in CIS countries and far abroad [Abdullazhanov B.R., 2014; Igolkin A.N., 2020; Mamadiev A.M., 2023].

A number of researchers consider 5-6 months to be the optimal time for performing RVR, which is associated with the adhesive process in the abdominal cavity [Akhrameev V.B., 2021; Baek S.J., 2014]. At the same time, Grushko S.A. et al. [2005], terms from 6 to 12 months are considered optimal. An alternative point of view is held by Ilkanich A.Ya. et al. (2016), which recommend performing RVT at an earlier date – 7-10 days without the risk of postoperative complications [Ilkanich A.Ya., 2016].

However, some researchers recommend following an individual and differentiated approach [Azizov B.D., 2018]. At the same time, Esin V.I. et al. (2016) note the leading role of the surgeon's experience in performing RVR [Yesin V.I., 2016].

Currently, the elimination of ileostomy and the completion of the recovery stage is an extremely important problem, since in most cases it is more difficult to form an ileostomy and is accompanied by the development of a number of complications. In recent years, there has been a tendency to reduce the time of dental care. Thus, there are recommendations for the implementation of the RVR in terms of 1 or more months [Gataullin I.G., 2016].

Some surgeons note that the closure of the stoma should occur no earlier than 60-90 days, since intra-abdominal adhesions become more manageable, and inflammation and edema resolve [Botirov J.A., 2022; Figueiredo M.N., 2015]. It is even indicated that the colostomy can be closed without discharge from the hospital, i.e. within 1 month after its formation [Ilkanich A.Ya., 2016; Darwin V.V., 2018].

A number of surgeons consider the optimal timing to be 3-4 months, 5-6 months [Khozhaev A.A., 2017; Baek S.J., 2014]. Grushko S.A. et al. [2005] recommends conducting an RVR in the period from 6 to 12 months.

The longest periods of stomatology are observed in patients who have undergone surgery for non-specific inflammatory bowel diseases. Therapy aimed at relieving inflammation increases the duration of stomatology. The formation of a stoma on the background of peritonitis also prolongs the duration of stomatology. During the recovery stage, preference is given to the intra-abdominal method [Timerbulatov V.M. et al., 2019]. However, in oncological diseases, the terms of surgical rehabilitation remain within 9-18 months [Batirov Zh.A., 2023; Mamadiev A.M., 2023]. This circumstance is associated with a possible recurrence of the tumor and makes it possible to diagnose it. Some surgeons associate the delay in the recovery stage with chemotherapy [Shabbir J., 2010].

In case of non-tumor diseases that led to the formation of an intestinal stoma, it is possible to reduce the stomatal period to 3-4 months. Individual researchers in a similar situation indicate the possibility of surgical rehabilitation in 1-2 months. It should be noted that in 6-32% of cases temporary stomas may turn out to be permanent [Khozhaev A.A., 2017; Chiu A., 2014]. Shabbir J. Et al. (2010) note that prolonged stomatology may be accompanied by the development of complications [Shabbir J., 2010]. The reason for permanent stomatitis may be old age, the development of anastomosis failure, metastatic lesion and adjuvant chemotherapy [Chiu A., 2014].

When forming an intestinal anastomosis, the technique of forming an intestinal anastomosis with a double-row suture is most often used, however, these techniques are time-consuming and there is a risk of anastomosis strictures [Madazimov M.M., 2022]. There are also supporters of the formation of an interstitial joint with a single-row seam [Élthes E., 2020].

A comparative assessment of the frequency of NA, depending on the method of formation of the anastomosis, did not reveal significant differences [Mildzikhov G.U., 2017; Majumder A., 2016]. In this regard, discussions are still ongoing about the advantages of each of the methods [Tomnyuk N.D., 2021; Batirov J.A., 2023; Kaneko T., 2019].

Currently, comparing the results of both techniques, individual researchers have not found a difference between them. However, manual methods of forming interstitial anastomoses remain popular due to the availability of the method [Kaneko T., 2019].

Conclusion. Thus, today there is a steady increase in intestinal diseases requiring surgical treatment. At the same time, there is a steady increase in the number of stomatized patients who require reconstructive surgery. It is alarming that disagreements remain in determining the timing of the RVR, there are no specific recommendations and a therapeutic and diagnostic algorithm of actions and a perfect ITA method modeling the valve function of the bauginia flap. It should be noted that the search continues, and it is justified, because it is aimed at improving the results of surgical treatment of this contingent of patients.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullajanov B.R., Botirov J.A. Analysis of the results of reconstructive restoration operations in picked patients // Materials of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference "The use of highly innovative technologies in preventive medicine." Andijan-2020. 637.
2. Abdullajanov B.R., Otakuziev A.Z., Nishanov M.F., Akbarov X.R. Features of reconstructive surgical interventions after operation of the type of Gatman // Achievements and prospects for the development of medical science. Materials of a year-old scientific and practical conference of young scientists TSMU them. Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Dushanbe 2014. P. 157-158.
3. Agaev E.K. Insolvency of seams of intestinal anastomosis in patients after emergency and emergency resection of the intestine / E.K. Agayev // Surgery. Magazine them. N. Pirogov. - 2012, -№ 1. -C. 34-37.
4. Agayev E.K., Ismaylova Z.E., Mamedov T.E. Prevention of insolvency of intestinal anastomoses seams // Surgery news. -2022; 30 (1): 86-94.
5. Azizov B.D., Asadov S.K., Davlatov A.R., Bobonazarova G.Sh. Features of preoperative preparation, methods and deadlines for the closure of intestinal stomters in children// Izvestia Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tajikistan. Department of Biological and Medical Sciences. - 2018. - № 1 (200). - P. 89-96.
6. Aliyev F.Sh., Azizov S.B., Aliyev V.F. and others. Problem issues of emergency surgery of the right half of the colon // Medical science and education of the Urals. 2017; 1 (89): 141-147.
7. Akhmetzyanov F.Sh., Valiev N.A., Egorov V.I. et al. Emergency surgical treatment tactics for obtuctive intestinal obstruction caused by colorectal cancer // Russian Journal of Gastroenterology, hepatology, coloproctology. -2018. -T.28, №1. -C. 99-106.
8. Akhrameev V.B., Grintsov A.G., Antonyuk S.M. et al. Features of reconstructive-reducing operations in patients after obstructive resection of the colon // Unemomial and rehabilitary surgery. -2021. Volume 6. №3. -C. 13-16.
9. Botirov J.A. Optimization of surgical tactics after the operation of the Gatman // Author's abstract. Diss. ... Cand. honey. Mr. AUC. Andijan. -2023. -56c.
10. Botirov J.A. Reconstructive restoration interventions after the operation of Gatman: problems and solutions // New day in medicine. -Bukhara, 2022. # 4(42) P.98-101. (14.00.00. №22).
11. Volenko P.A. Comparative assessment of the results of using ASK and AK devices for the formation of circular compression anastomoses in the surgery of the digestive tract: author. Diss. ... Cand. honey. Spider // Moscow. - 2006. - 26 p.
12. Vorobev G.I., Shelygin Yu.A., Eropkin P.V. et al. Application of hardware and manual seam when closing preventive ie // Annals surgery. - 2008. - № 4. - P. 40-44.

13. Harmanova TN, Kazachenko E.A., Krylov N.N. From the history of surgery: the evolution of views on the formation of intestinal stoma // Magazine: the history of medicine. -2019. Volume 6, №2, p.151-159.
14. Gatullin I.G., Khalikov M.M. Analysis of the immediate and remote results of the reconstructive restoration stage after the operations of the type of Gatmann // Coloproctology. -2016. -№ 1 (55). -C. 22-26.
15. Hibert B.K., Matveev N.A., Borodin N.A. et al. The value of the anatomy of the cooler and turned off from the passage of the colon departments after obstructive resection during regenerative operations.Herald of surgery. -2018. T.177, №2., -C.34-38.
16. Hibert B.K., Khasia D.T., Matveev I.A., Matveev A.I., Kalinichenko A.P. Experience as a factor in improving the results of laparoscopic restoration interventions in patients with End colostomias // Coloproctology. - 2017. - № 4 (62) - P. 24-29.
17. Glushkov N.I., Gorshenin T.L., Dulaev S.K. Immediate results of surgical treatment of complicated colon cancer in patients of elderly and senile age // Successes gerontology. -2018; 31 (4): 574-580.
18. Gordeev S.A. Combined and simultaneous laparoscopic operations // Celt: Multidisciplinary Medical Center. - Access mode: https://www.celt.ru/articles/art/art_31.phtml, Free (date of handling: 02.02.2020).
19. Grushko S.A., Tokarsky A.N., Atoyan G.N. [and others] individualization of methods of rehabilitation of patients after the operation of Gatmann // Actual problems of coloproctology: theses of the reports of the scientific conference with international participation dedicated to the 40th anniversary of the SSC of Coloproctology. - M., 2005. - P. 203-205.
20. Darwin V.V., Krasnov E.A., Dobalyuk A.V. et al. Insolvency of the anastomoses during operations over the cancer of the sigmoid and rectum: the frequency of occurrence, the way of improving the results // Coloproctology. - 2018. - № 2S (64). - P. 39.
21. Esin V.I., Khalov V.Yu., Yunusov A.Sh., Bondarenko A.A. On the timing of the elimination of intestinal stomas // Coloproctology. -2016. - № 1 (55). - P. 109-110.
22. Igolekin A.N., Polovinkin V.V. Reconstructive restoration interventions on the colon after the operation of Gatmann: problems and solutions. Innovative medicine Kuban.2020; (4): 51-57.
23. Ilkanich A.Ya., Darwin V.V., Krasnov E.A. [and others] The choice of restoration intervention in patients with толстокишечными Stommas // Coloproctology. -2016. - № 1 (55). - P. 110.
24. Ilchenko A.A., Musician TA Excess bacterial growth syndrome in the small intestine: etiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations // Experimental and clinical gastroenterology. -2009. -№ 5. -C. 99-108.
25. Caprin A.D., Starinsky V.V., Petrova G.V. The state of oncological assistance to the population of Russia in 2018. Стоквa. 2019; 236.
26. Kondratyuk A.I., Kovrga A.I. Differentiated tactics of treatment of a colon withdrawn by perforation, taking into account the risk of insolvency of intercheque anastomoses // Science and healthcare. -2018; 20 (3): 45-59.
27. Korolev P.A., Sidorov D.V., Slakin M.V. et al. Multivisceral resection in the treatment of caravan cancer // Oncology. Magazine them. Pa Herzen. -2018. # 7 (4). P. 46-51.

28. Majimov M.M., Botirov A.K., Botirov J.A., Sulonov H.S. Modified techniques and technical techniques for reconstructive reducing operations about left-sided colostomas// New day in medicine. -Bukhara, 2022.# 9(47) p.357-361.(14.00.00. №22).
29. Mamadiev A.M. Ways to improve the results of surgical treatment and rehabilitation of acute left-sided thick-binded obstruction // Author. Diss. ... Cand. honey.Mr.AUC. Andijan. -2023. -48c.
30. Manikhas G.M., Khanyevich MD, Friedman M.Kh., Miller A.E. The use of crosslinking apparatuses in colon cancer surgery // Coloproctology. - 2010. - № 4. - C. 13-16.
31. Mildzikhov GG, Totikov V.Z., Pagieva M.K. et al. Analysis of microcirculatory disorders in the zone of formed thin-column anastomosis // infection in surgery. - 2017. - T. 15, №2. -C. 3-5.
32. Niyozbekhov B.M., Rzaev T.Z., Khalilov Z.B., Chinikov M.A. Miniinvasive interventions in the urgent surgery of the colon // Surgery. Journal named after N.I. Pirogov. - 2020. - № 6. - P. 109-113.
33. Polovinkinkin V.V., Igolkin A.N., Prin P.S., Agadzhanyan D.Z. a method for the formation of access to the "short" cult of the rectum with reconstructive restoration operations on the colon.Innovative medicine Kuban. 2016; 1: 64-7 .;
34. Salamakhin MP, Leonov O.V., Dergacheva T.S. and others. A new way to form a laparoscopic intracorporal term-terminal Ileotransversoanastomosis //Innovative Medicine Kuban. -2020; (1): 30-35.
35. Selnagina L.A., Vorobey A.V., Vijinis E.I. et al. Results of surgical treatment of complicated cancer of the right flank of the colon //BGMU in the forefront of medical science and practice. -2015; (5): 178-182.
36. Soloviev I.A., Pershko A.M., Kurilo D.P. and others. Tactics of surgical treatment of complications of crown disease //Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy. -2018; 1 (61): 111-116.
37. Spiery V.V., Luntovsky A.M. Methods for the formation of fine-color anastomoses with complicated cancer right half of the colon //University medicine of the Urals.-2017; 3 (1): 65-66.
38. Stoyko Y.M., Maksimenkov A.V., Levchuk A.L., Kolozyan D.A. Laparoscopic reconstructive restoration operations on the colon//Bulletin of the National Medical and Surgical Center. N. Pirogova 2019, vol. 14, No. 1. -c., 36-40.
39. Timerbulatov V.M., Timerbulatov M.V. Classification of surgical complications // Surgery. - 2018. -№ 9. -s. 61-65.
40. Timerbulatov M.V., Ibatullin A.A., Gainutdinov F.M. et al. Modification of the closure method of a stomal wound after reconstructive restoration operations // Coloproctology. - 2019. -M. 18, No. 3. -C. 98-99.
41. Timerbulatov M.V., Ibatullin A.A., Gainutdinov F.M. et al. Comparison of methods of stomal wounds when conducting reconstructive restoration operations // Medical Basket Bashkartaston, 2018 Volume 13, No. 5 (77).-with66-68.
42. Tomnyuk N.D., Khovalyg V.S., Municipality A.M. [and others]. Restoration of the continuity of the colon after operation of the type of Gatman: difficulties and their decision // International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research. - 2021. - № 1. - p. 15-18.

43. Torchinsky N.V., Kamenskaya A.Y. Epidemiological manifestations of the incidence of colon cancer (colon cancer) in the Russian Federation // In the book: Infectious diseases in the modern world: epidemiology, diagnosis, treatment and prevention. Collection of works of the XII Annual All-Russian Web of Congress In infectious diseases with international participation. Moscow; -2020: 226-227.
44. Totikov Z.V., Totikov V.Z., Kachmazov A.K., Medoev V.V. The method of prevention of insolvency anastomosis after the front rectification of the rectum and reconstructive restoration operations / Kuban scientific medical school. - 2013. - № 4 (139). - C. 109-111.
45. Fedorov V.D., Vorobyva G.I., Rivkin V.L. Clinical Operational Coloproctology: Guide for Doctors / Ed. - M.: SSC Proctology, 1994. -432 p.
46. Fedorov E.V., Savushkin A.V., Khachaturova E.A. and others. Forum of Anesthesiologists and Resuscitations of Russia (Farre 2019) - M., 2019. - 318 p.
47. Khevaev A.A. Reconstructive surgical rehabilitation with colorectal cancer (literature review) // Bulletin of Surgery of Kazakhstan. -2017. -№ 2 (51). -C. 50-60.
48. Tsarkov P.V., Tulina I.A., Tsugulu P.B. and others. Choosing a method for forming a preventive intestinal stoma after rectification resection: protocol of prospective multicenter randomized clinical research // Russian Journal of Gastroenterology, hepatology, coloproctology. -2017; 27 (2): 102-110.
49. Cherdantsev D.V., Pozdnyakov A.A., Shpak V.V. and others. Analysis of complications after abdominal operations on the colon // Modern problems of science and education. 2017; (2): 78.
50. Yakomaskin V.N., Ravich L.D., Semencheva N.V. The experience of laparoscopic reconstructive operations on the colon [Text] / V. N. Yakomaskin // Almanac of the Institute of Surgery. Vishnevsky. -2019. - № - p. 368.
51. Baek S.J., Kim S.h., Lee C.K. [et al.] Relationship Between The Severity Of Diversion Colitis And The Composition Of Colonic Bacteria: A Prospective Study // GUT LIVER. -2014. -Vol. 8, No. 2. - P. 170-176.
52. Baumann P., Kim J., Ahn S.H. [et al.] Mid-Term Absorbable Monofilament IS Safe and Effective for Gastrointestinal Anastomosis - Promegat - A Single-Arm Prospective Observational Study // Ann. Med. Surg. -2018. -Vol. 30. - P. 1-6.
53. Chiu A., Chan H.T., Brown C.J. [et al.] Failing to Reverse A Diverting Stoma After Lower Anterior Resection of Recal Cancer // AM. J. Surg. -2014. -Vol. 207, №5. -P.708-711.
54. Davis C.H., Shirkey B.A., Moore L.W. et al. Trends in Laparoscopic Colorectal Surgery Over Time From 2005-2014 using the nsqip database. J Surg Res. 2018 Mar; 223: 16-21.
55. Élthes E., Sala D., Neagoer R.m. et al. Safety of Anastomotic Techniques and Consequences of Anastomotic Leakage in Patients With Colorectal Cancer: A Single Surgeon Experience // Medicine and Pharmacy Reports. -2020 Oct; 93(4): 384-389.
56. Emile S., Elfeki H., Shalaby M. et al. INTRACORPOREAL VERSUS EXTRA-Corporeal Anastomosis in Minimally Invasive Right Colectomy: An Updated Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis // Tech Coloproctol. -2019 Nov; 23(11): 1023-1035.
57. Figueiredo M.N., Mège D., Maggiori L. [et al.] WHEN IS THE BEST TIME FOR TEMPORARY STOMA Closure in laparoscopic SPHInctersaving Surgery for Rectal Cancer? A Study of 259 Consecutive Patients // Tech. Coloproctol. -2015. -Vol. 19, No. 8. - P. 469-474.

58. Kaneko T., Funahashi K., USHIGOME M. Incidence of and Risk Factors for Incisional Hernia After Closure of Temporary Ileostomy For colorectal malignancy // *Hernia*. - 2019. - Vol. 23, No. 4. - P. 743-748.
59. Majumder A., Winder J.S., Wen Y. [et al.] Comparative Analysis of BioLogic Versus Synthetic Mesh Outcomes in Contaminated Hernia Repair // *Surgery*. -2016. -Vol. 160, No. 4. -p. 828-838.
60. MAO D., Rey-Conde T., North J.B.Et al.Critical Analysis of the Causes of In-Hospital Mortality Following Colorectal Resection: A Queensland Audit of Surgical Mortality (QASM) Registry Study // *World Journal of Surgery*.-2022; 46(7): 1796-1804.
61. Moro-Valdezate D., Royo-Aznar A., Martín-Arévalo J. et al. Outcomes of Hartmann's Procedure and Subsequent Intestinal Restoration. Which Patients Are Most Likely to Undergo Reversal? *AmJ SURG*. -2019; -218: 918-27.
62. Shabbir J., Britton D.C. Stoma Complications: A Literature Overview // *Colorectal Dis*. -2010. -Vol. 12, No. 10. -p. 958-964.
63. Shin J.K., Kim H.CH., Lee W.Y. et al. Laparoscopic Modified Mesocolic Excision With Central Vascular Ligation in Right-Sided Colon Cancer Shows Better Short- and Long-Term Outcomes compared with the open approach in propensity score analysis. *SURG ENDOSC*. 2018; 32(6): 2721-2731.
64. Siegel R.L., Miller K.D., Jemal A. Cancer Statistics, 2019. // *CA CANCER J CLIN*. -2019; 69(1): 7-34.
65. Tang T., Abu-Sbeih H., MA W.Et al.Gastrointestinal Injury Related to Antiangiogenesis Cancer Therapy // *Clinical Colorectal Cancer*.-2020; 19(3): 117-123.
66. Tarta C., Bishawi, Bergamaschi R. INTRACORPOREAL ILEOCOLIC ANASTOMOSIS: A REVIEW. *Tech ColoproCTOL*. 2013; 17(5): 479-485.
67. Wu Q., Jin C., Hu T., Wei M. Intracorporeal Versus Extracorporeal Anastomosis in Laparoscopic Right Colectomy: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J LaparoEndosc ADV Surg Techn*. 2017; 27(4): 348- 357.
68. Zhu Y., Chen J., Lin S., Xu D. Risk Factor for the Development of Surgical Site Infection Following Ileostomy Reversal: A Single- Center Report // *Updates in Surgery*.-2022; 74(5): 1675-1682.